

AEROELASTIC ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Aeroelastic phenomenon is required to be studied for design and development of aircraft, particularly for high speed as well as high aspect ratio wing. In the design of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), the flutter speed has to be estimated and sufficient dive speed to flutter speed margin has to be established to ensure the safety of the UAVs. The interaction of the elastic, inertia and aerodynamic forces is a dynamic phenomenon resulting in flutter. Flutter will occur when the artificial structural damping equals the actual damping of the structure. It is computed using velocity-damping method by idealizing the wing as the plate. Flutter speed is a function of structural properties like mass distribution, stiffness of the structure. If the structure is made up of composite material, the stiffness is dependent on the characteristics of the laminates namely thickness, material, fiber orientation of the individual lamina and number of such laminas that make up the laminate. Modelling of the composite laminates (UDL) have been carried out using Ansys with required laminate sequence and fiber orientations to capture the bending and torsion modes. This paper highlights velocity-damping (v-g) method with a case study applied to a general composite laminate and studies how the laminate fiber orientation angles affect the flutter speed. This study will result in having optimum laminate properties to postpone the dynamic instability. An attempt has been made to address the aeroelastic analysis of multifunctional composites.

1.0 Introduction:

With an advent of emerging technologies, tailoring of composites for suitable applications is indeed a challenge in the current industry scenario. Fiber reinforced composite laminates are increasingly being used in the construction of the aerospace, mechanical, civil, marine, automotive and other high performance structures due to their high specific stiffness and strength. The present study involves numerical and experimental works to investigate the modal analysis of the composite uni-directional fiber Glass/Epoxy composite plate for cantilevered boundary conditions replicating the wing of the unmanned aerial vehicles. Experimental modal analysis with an impact hammer for a particular layup sequence (0/-45/-45/+45/0)_s is conducted to validate the numerical model. The specimens of glass fibre and epoxy matrix composite plates are manufactured by the hand-layup technique using vacuum method and cured under room temperature. An experimental investigation is carried out to obtain the Natural frequencies and mode shapes using Dytran accelerometer 3032A

,mini modal hammer 2031. Bending and Torsion mode shapes are utilized in plotting the velocity-Damping curves. The work is extended for other laminate sequences and multi-functional composites to show the impact of fiber orientation angle on the dynamic instability of the wing type structures.

2.0 Aeroelastic Flutter Problem

The flutter problem is formulated using an indirect method widely known as the u-g method^[1]. In this method, the structural damping coefficient (g), introduced into the equations of motion is plotted versus velocity for each vibration mode. Since solutions to the equations to the motion represent conditions for neutral stability, the value of g obtained in this manner represents the amount of damping that must be added to the structure to attain neutral stability (flutter) at the given Velocity. Flutter will occur when the artificial structural damping equals the actual damping of the Structure. To simplify calculations, the flutter problem will be formulated using only the equations of motion from the two-term deflection equation. As a first step strain energy of the anisotropic plate^[5]

$V = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \int_{-c/2}^{+c/2} \nabla^2 \nabla^2 w dy dx$ gets modified to

the composite as given below,

$$\frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \int_{-c/2}^{+c/2} \left[D_{11}(W_{,xx})^2 + 2D_{12}W_{,xx}W_{,yy} + D_{22}(W_{,yy})^2 + 4D_{16}W_{,xx}W_{,xy} + 4D_{26}W_{,yy}W_{,xy} + 4D_{66}(W_{,xy})^2 \right] dy dx \quad (2.1)$$

where $D_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n [Q_{ij}^k] [Z_k^3 - Z_{k-1}^3] / 3$

As a second step the kinetic energy of the plate can be written as

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \int_{-c/2}^{+c/2} m \left\{ \dot{\omega} \right\}^2 dx dy, \quad (2.2)$$

where $m = \rho_w t_w$, where ρ_w is the specific gravity of the wing structure and t_w is the thickness of the wing.

As a third step the Lagrange's equation [7] is given as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{q}_i} \right) + \frac{\partial V}{\partial q_i} - \frac{\partial T}{\partial q_i} = Q_i \quad (2.3)$$

Assuming sinusoidal motion for the vibration mode and neglecting warping stiffness of the structure, the equations of motion can be written as

$$-\omega^2 [M_{ij}] \begin{Bmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \end{Bmatrix} + [K_{ij}] \begin{Bmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} Q_1 / e^{i\omega t} \\ Q_2 / e^{i\omega t} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2.4)$$

Where

$$[M_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} mclI_4 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{mclI_5}{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad (2.5)$$

$$[K_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{D_{11}cI_7}{l^3} & \frac{2D_{16}I_6}{l^3} \\ \frac{2D_{16}I_6}{l^2} & \frac{4D_{66}I_8}{cl} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.6)$$

I_4, I_5, I_6, I_7, I_8 are Non-dimensional integral expressions as given in [6]

The aerodynamic forces acting on the structure [8] can written as

$$L_E = \omega^2 \pi \rho b^3 \left[\{L_1 + iL_2\} \frac{W_E}{b} + \{L_3 + iL_4\} \alpha \right] e^{i\omega t}$$

$$L_1 + iL_2 = 1 - \frac{2i}{k} c(k)$$

$$L_3 + iL_4 = a + \frac{2c(k)}{k^2} + \frac{i}{k} [1 + (1-2a)c(k)]$$

$$M_E = \omega^2 \pi \rho b^4 \left[\{M_1 + iM_2\} \frac{W_E}{b} + \{M_3 + iM_4\} \alpha \right] e^{i\omega t}$$

$$M_1 + iM_2 = 1 - \frac{i(1+2a)}{k} c(k)$$

$$M_3 + iM_4 = \left(\frac{1}{8} + a^2 \right) + \frac{(1+2a)c(k)}{k^2} + \frac{i}{k} \left[\left(\frac{1}{2} - 2a^2 \right) c(k) - \left(\frac{1}{2} - a \right) \right]$$

$$Q_1 = \omega \pi \rho b^3 \{ [L_1 + iL_2] U_4 q_1 / b + [L_3 + iL_4] U_3 q_2 / c \} e^{i\omega t}$$

$$Q_2 = \omega^2 \pi \rho b^4 \{ [M_1 + iM_2] U_3 q_1 / bc + [M_3 + iM_4] U_3 q_2 / c \} e^{i\omega t}$$

The flutter problem can be formulated as

$$[K - \omega^2 A] \{q\} = 0$$

Where the stiffness matrix K and aerodynamic matrix A [4] are defined below

$$\begin{aligned} K_{11} &= cD_{11}I_7/l^3 \\ K_{12} &= 2D_{16}I_6/l^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

$$K_{21} = 2D_{16}I_6/l^2$$

$$K_{22} = 4D_{66}I_8/cl$$

$$A_{11} = mclI_4 + \pi \rho b I_4 [L_1 + iL_2]$$

$$A_{12} = \pi \rho b^3 I_3 / c [L_1 + iL_2]$$

$$A_{21} = \pi \rho b^3 I_3 / c [M_1 + iM_2]$$

$$A_{22} = mclI_5/12 + \pi \rho b^4 I_5 / c^2 [M_1 + iM_2] \quad (2.8)$$

c = chord length of the wing

The flutter frequency ω , the damping ratio g and the flutter speed u are extracted as

$$\omega = 1/\sqrt{\text{Real}(z)}$$

$$g = \text{imaginary}(z)/\text{real}(z)$$

$$u = b\omega/k, \quad b = \text{semi chord length and}$$

$$k = \text{strouhl number}$$

The algorithm is iterated for different suitable values of k till the damping ratio becomes zero.

Fig-1: Wind tunnel model of the aerofoil wing

3.0 Estimation of flutter speed of an Aerofoil

The Idealized Mathematical model of the wing to estimate the flutter speed is shown in Fig. 1. The wing airfoil is assumed to be thin and the motion is assumed as simple harmonic. Hence the second order linear coupled differential equation of the system, in generalized coordinates can be written as ^[10]

$$m\ddot{h} + s_\alpha \ddot{\alpha} + m\omega_h^2 h = Q_h \quad (3.1)$$

$$s_\alpha \ddot{h} + I_\alpha \ddot{\alpha} + I_\alpha \omega_\alpha^2 h = Q_\alpha$$

and the corresponding flutter determinant is given by :

$$\begin{vmatrix} \left\{ \frac{m}{\pi \rho b^3} \left[1 - \frac{\omega_h^2 \omega_\alpha^2}{\omega_\alpha^2 \omega_h^2} \right] + L_h \right\} & \left\{ x_\alpha \frac{m}{\pi \rho b^3} + L_\alpha - L_h \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha \right) \right\} \\ \left\{ x_\alpha \frac{m}{\pi \rho b^3} + \frac{1}{2} - L_h \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha \right) \right\} & \left\{ r_\alpha^2 \frac{m}{\pi \rho b^3} \left[1 - \frac{\omega_h^2}{\omega_\alpha^2} \right] + M_\alpha \right. \\ & \left. - \left(\frac{1}{2} + L_\alpha \right) \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha \right) + L_h \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha \right)^2 \right\} \end{vmatrix} \quad (3.2)$$

Analytical code in MatLab has been developed to evaluate (3.2). The flutter speed can be obtained by letting the determinant to go to zero. Some of the variables used in the code are listed below

$$C(k) = F(k) + iG(k) = \frac{H_1^{(2)}(k)}{H_1^{(2)}(k) + iH_0^{(2)}(k)} \quad (3.3)$$

Where C(k) is the Theodorsen function expressed as Hankel functions.

4.0 Computation of Laminate stiffness matrix

The stiffness of the laminate is computed by adding up the stiffness of each sub-element in all layers in the laminate including the interface layer. The elemental stiffness matrix is computed by relating the *ABD* matrix of the lamina to the element strain matrix as shown in^[3]

$$K = \iint [B_i^T (A)_{ABD} B_i + B_i^T (B)_{ABD} B_o + B_o^T (B)_{ABD} B_i + B_o^T (D)_{ABD} B_o] J d\xi d\eta \quad (4.1)$$

Where,

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \xi} \\ \frac{\partial x}{\partial \eta} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \eta} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.2)$$

K is the lamina sub element stiffness matrix [20 × 20], *B_i* is the in-plane strain-displacement matrix [3 × 8], *B_o* is the out-of-plane strain-displacement matrix [3 × 12], (*A*)_{ABD} is the extensional stiffness [3 × 3] of the lamina, (*B*)_{ABD} is the coupling stiffness [3 × 3] of the lamina, (*D*)_{ABD} is the bending stiffness [3 × 3] of the lamina, and *J* is the Jacobian matrix. In terms of the FEM description, each lamina is modeled by a four-node lamina sub-element. The corresponding arrangements of nodes and degrees of freedom (DOF) are shown in Figure 1(b). The numbering of nodes in the lamina sub-element is arranged in anticlockwise manner and each node has 5 DOF which include displacements in *x*, *y*,

and z -directions (u , v , and w , resp.) as well as rotations about y - and x -directions (θ_x and θ_y , resp.). The displacements of lamina sub-element are expressible as

$$\begin{aligned} u &= [N_i] \{u_i\}; \\ v &= [N_i] \{v_i\}; \\ w &= [N_o] \{w_i\}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

where N_i and N_o are, respectively, the in-plane Lagrange shape function and out-of-plane polynomial shape function of a nonconforming rectangular element with 12 terms. In detail, $\{u_i\} = \{u_1 \ u_2 \ u_3 \ u_4\}^T$, $\{v_i\} = \{v_1 \ v_2 \ v_3 \ v_4\}^T$, and $\{w_i\} = \{w_1 \ \theta_{1x} \ \theta_{1y} \ w_2 \ \theta_{2x} \ \theta_{2y} \ w_3 \ \theta_{3x} \ \theta_{3y} \ w_4 \ \theta_{4x} \ \theta_{4y}\}^T$.

5.0 Results and Discussion

Case-1: Laminate configuration: [0 -45 -45 45 0]_s Modal analysis validation and V-g Plots

Ten layered Laminate have been chosen to experimentally validate the numerical model carried out using Ansys. Shell-181^[11] have been used to model the laminate. Modal analysis validation have been carried out using ME scope an

The stiffness matrices of the lamina sub-elements are assembled in the local stiffness matrix of the laminate element as follows:

$$K_{LAM} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{Lower} & K_{null} \\ K_{null} & K_{upper} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.4)$$

where K_{LAM} is the stiffness matrix $[40 \times 40]$ of laminate element, K_{lower} is the stiffness matrix $[20 \times 20]$ of bottom lamina sub element, K_{null} is the null matrix $[20 \times 20]$, and K_{upper} is the stiffness matrix $[20 \times 20]$ of top lamina sub element.

analysis software used to capture the relevant modes of the composite laminate. The results obtained from the analysis and the modal analysis carried out using block Lanczos method are in a close match for the laminate chosen with the following properties $E_x=E_y=31\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{xy} = 0.15$ and $G_{xy}= 7\text{GPa}$

Fig-2: Modal Extraction positions

Fig-3 : 16.3Hz, Mode-1: Bending

Fig-4 : 16.5Hz, Mode-1: Bending

Fig-5 : 103Hz, Mode-2: Torsion

Fig-6: 1st Torsion: Natural Frequency -107Hz

Fig-7 : V-g Plot for the laminate configuration:
: [0 -45 -45 45]_s

Case-2 : Laminate configuration: [0 -45 -45 45]_s Modal analysis and V-g Plots with laminate properties of $E_x=50$ GPa $E_y=15$ GPa, $\rho_{xy} = 0.25$ and $G_{xy}= 3.5$ GPa

Fig-8 : V-g Plot for the laminate configuration : [0 -45 -45 45]_s

Case-3 : Laminate configuration: [0 0 0 90]_s Modal analysis and V-g Plots with laminate properties of $E_x=50$ GPa $E_y=15$ GPa, $\rho_{xy} = 0.25$ and $G_{xy}= 3.5$ GPa

Fig-9: V-g Plot for the laminate configuration : [0 0 0 90]_s

Case-4: Laminate configuration: [0 45 0 90] s Modal analysis and V-g Plots with laminate properties of $E_x=50$ GPa $E_y=15$ GPa, $\nu_{xy} = 0.25$ and $G_{xy}= 3.5$ GPa

Fig-10: V-g Plot for the laminate configuration : [0 45 0 90]s

Case-5: Multifunctional Laminate configuration: [0 45 0 0] s Modal analysis and V-g Plots

The laminate chosen is shown in fig-11 [3] has a PLI stacked in the eight plied

Configuration and the properties of the lamina are given in the Table-1. PLI batteries are stacked at 0^0 fiber orientation. Batteries are orientation have been intentionally kept at 0^0 to compute the dynamic instability.

Fig-11: Laminate configuration of Multifunctional composite

Material	Young's Modulus, E(GPa)	Density (kg/m ³)	Thickness (mm)	Orientation(Deg)(No. of Layers)
Carbon Epoxy	72.40	1100	0.15	0/45/45/0
Packaging	4.60	1290	0.20	0/0 (2 Layers)
PLI	1.02	2540	0.50	0/0 (2 Layers)

Table-1: Properties of Lamina used in Multifunctional composite lay-up^[3]

Case-5: Laminate configuration: [0 45 0 90] s Modal analysis and V-g Plots

Fig-12: V-g Plot for the laminate configuration : [0 45 0 90]s

6.0 CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of the work was to study the effect of laminate orientation on the flutter speed for the composite laminates. The study was carried out for three different material configurations, each having the specific orientation angle suitable for the design of small scaled unmanned aerial vehicle. From the results, it is clear that the flutter speed is maximum for a orientation dominated by the 45° plies. This is because of the fact that the torsional stiffness (GJ) influences more on the flutter speed. The design for maximizing

the ILSS involves distributing more number of 45° plies in a suitable manner, which in a way enhances the flutter speed. However with a multifunctional composite the flutter speed can further be postponed.

In summary, aero elastic tailoring of aircraft wings can be an effective tool for enhancing the flutter speed margin of the aircraft. The future work is to include thermal and electrical effects in the computation of flutter speed for multifunctional composites

7.0 REFERENCES

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